

Exploring the Natural Ventilation System of Biomimetic Solar-Powered African Termite Mounds Using Computer Simulated Models for Varied Building Configurations

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ABSTRACT:

With the drastic increase in energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in recent decades, there is an urgent need for more efficient buildings. To aid in these efforts, this research explored a biomimetic approach to building ventilation by analyzing the natural ventilation system in solar-powered African termite mounds (ATM) using nine building configurations with the aid of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) software. Eight different building orientations were simulated, each with two wall opening percentages, and two building depths, and applied to both midrise and high-rise structures. Results show that operative temperatures of the ATM ventilation systems were significantly lower compared to the conventional models by seven degrees. Additionally, there is a consistent result of lower wind velocities for the ATM ventilation system in all types of building footprints tested. The bio-mimetic approach with the ATM-inspired ventilation system provides a practical blueprint for an energy efficient future in building ventilation system design.

Keywords: Building Ventilation, Energy Efficiency, Architecture, Building Systems, Engineering, Biomimicry, Sustainability.

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INTRODUCTION

Recent statistics show that global energy consumption has been increasing at a fast rate for decades. A large percentage of this comes from buildings and their operations, which contribute 36% to energy consumption and 40% to CO₂ emissions [1]. Buildings implement heating and cooling solutions to provide maximum comfort to its users, and most often, especially in developing countries like the Philippines, this is through the use of mechanical equipment that consume large amounts of energy on a daily basis, particularly in large-scale establishments such as high-rise buildings where common passive cooling strategies are difficult to apply.

To address this problem, several buildings around the globe are starting to promote renewable energy and sustainable technologies with low to nearly zero energy consumption. The goal being to design more sustainable buildings with less harmful environmental impacts. One of the increasingly explored approaches to this enterprise is biomimicry [2]. This approach emulates the strategies, processes or patterns found in nature which is believed to have been filtered to its best through millions of years of evolution and genetic lineage. Termites and their mounds are one of the most common inspirations cited in biomimicry. A complex system of tunnels and air channels facilitate gas

exchange and improve ventilation in the mound, hence providing the termites a suitable environment where they can thrive underground [3]. Because of this, termite mounds are excellent inspiration and scientific basis to achieve an efficient passive ventilation system in buildings that require little to no mechanical cooling equipment.

One of the known buildings inspired from termite mounds is the Eastgate Building in Zimbabwe. The building was designed by Ar. Mick Pearce and was based on the thermosiphon flow and induced flow model for termite mound ventilation [6]. However, for many termite mounds that only stand a few meters tall, the reliability of the vertical gradient of natural winds that travel in varying speed and directions are reduced and are unpredictable. Hence, induced flow can only rarely be found in termite mounds [9].

However, based on newer studies showing that termite mounds are driven by temporal variations in the wind [8], a natural ventilation system may be designed exploiting these temporal variations. Such ventilation system may include a wind capture device that acts as a gas exchange system. A chamber similar in function to the mound's chimney where air exchange can occur can be connected to the occupied spaces and surface conduits [10]. Moreover, new conclusions from termite mound studies indicating the diurnally oscillating thermal schedules due to solar heat are the dominant force driving mound ventilation, it can be studied and the system may be applied as a biomimetic inspiration to design a natural ventilation system.

By exploring the process applied in the ventilation of termite mounds, this study is an attempt to achieve energy efficiency through passive cooling. This will be done by investigating the air flow and temperature in building design integrated with the principles of the ventilation mechanism of termite mounds through virtual simulation models. The use of natural ventilation in buildings, particularly in large-scale midrise and high-rise buildings, reduces the reliance on energy for ventilation and space cooling demands, thus, reducing costs that is normally due to the use of mechanical air-conditioning systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The process of ventilation in African termite mounds was studied and analyzed, and a corresponding building analogy was designed. The following features of termite mounds were identified to be essential to the mound ventilation as described in related studies.

1. *Central chimney* – Buoyant air from the nest produced from the metabolism of the termite flow upward to the top of the chimney where they exit the mound through the porous soil of the mound
2. *Subterranean tunnels* – These tunnels surround the nest and they are dominated by buoyancy-driven air flow from the nest. Similar to the central chimney, warmer air from the nest flow upwards and is replaced by cool air that is denser and hence will sink.
3. *Egress tunnels* – These act as pores to the enclosed mound where intercepting winds are captured and enter the mound through forced convection.
4. *Surface conduits* – These vertical air passages that run from the top to the subterranean part of the mound are connected directly to the egress holes. They are dominated by forced convection because of the high frequency winds entering from the egress holes. These winds travel through the surface conduits to the subterranean tunnels and eventually reach the nest.
5. *Lateral connectives / reticulum* – This is a complex network of tunnels that connect the surface conduit, the central chimney and the nest. Both forced and natural convection are at work here.
6. *Nest* – The ventilation in the nest is dominated by natural convection, where the metabolism of the termites and the fungi drive a natural, convective flow where warmer air flows upwards and it is replaced by cooler air that ventilates the mound.

The next part of the study involved the building simulations. Building simulation models were created, integrating the natural ventilation system inspired from the natural ventilation process found in termite

mounds. Building models were classified into 9 building footprint shapes: *rectangular*, *triangular*, *trapezoidal*, *square atrium*, *cross-shape*, *H-shape*, *L-shape*, *U-shape*, *T-shape*. There were further classified by building height: *midrise* (10 floors) and *high-rise* (25 floors), percentage of wall opening: 44% and 78%, presence of interior partitions, room depth: $2h$ and $4h$ for models with interior partitions, and $5h$ and $9h$ for those with none, and building orientation: *N*, *S*, *E*, *W*, *NW*, *NE*, *SW*, *SE*.

Building simulation models were created with dimensions as illustrated below. Nine building footprint shapes were considered, with each footprint having 2 variations in terms of interior partitions. Partitionless interior was considered for cross-flow ventilation (Figure 2.1), and with interior partitions for single-sided ventilation (Figure 2.2). Simulation models with no interior partitions must have a room depth equal to $5h$ and $9h$, where h is the height from floor to the ceiling, equal to 2.70m (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Nine Building Footprints Considered where $x = 5h$ and $x = 9h$

Normal single-sided ventilation, on the other hand, must have a room depth of $2h$ and $4h$, where h is the height from floor to the ceiling, equal to 2.70m.

Figure 2. Nine Building Footprints Considered where $x = 2h$ and $x = 4h$

Research data and results were determined based on the effect to the wind flow rates and air flow of the following ventilation features added to create a natural ventilation system design. These features were translated from the processes and parts of African termite mounds that contribute and control its ventilation. They were then applied to the varied configurations of the nine different building footprint shapes to create a natural ventilation system design mimicked from the solar-powered ventilation of African termite mounds.

Figure 3. Building Simulation Set-Up.
 a) 10-Storey Midrise Building with Rectangular Shape with Configuration of 44% Wall Opening with Partitions and 2h Room Depth,
 b) Section Cut Through Stacks in Isometric View

Figure 4. Building Simulation Set-Up.
 a) 25-Storey High-Rise Building with Rectangular Shape with Configuration of 44% Wall Opening with Partitions and 2h Room Depth,
 b) Section Cut Through Stacks in Isometric View

In the ATM-inspired natural ventilation system design, additional building features were added that mimicked the parts and processes found in African termite mounds. The additional building features are as follows:

- a. Each building model configuration was added with an underfloor airspace with dimensions of 0.80m x 2.40m x 0.50m depth. These underfloor airspaces open to the outside through an opening with dimensions of 0.80m x 0.50m on the façade. Underfloor airspaces were placed on all sides of the building, spaced at 4.0 meters from each other.
- b. Vertical air spaces referred to as “stacks” in this paper were added in each building configuration, shown as dark-shaded areas in Figures 1 and 2. The dimensions of stacks vary depending on the shape of the building footprint and the depth configuration, but the total volume of the stacks were equal to 18% of the total volume of the building. The “main stack” or the chimney is placed in the center of the building shape, and is the biggest among the stacks.
- c. Each stack has an opening to each storey, with an opening height of 0.40 meters.
- d. All stacks are open on two sides, the top and the bottom to allow air inside to move and circulate. Openings offset the topmost part of the building by 1.80 meters for the smaller stacks and 3.00 meters for the main stack for the midrise building models, and 2.40 meters and 4.80 meters for the smaller stacks and main stack, respectively, for the high-rise building models.
- e. The 1st storey of the midrise building model, and the 1st and 14th storeys of the high-rise building model, are open with no rooms or partitions.

Figure 5. Architectural Elements of ATM-Inspired Natural Ventilation System Design

The simulation models were created using Trimble Sketchup and were exported to IES VE 2019. Under Building Properties, the location was set to Davao Francisco Bangoy International Airport and the Building HVAC service to default. The Building Type was set to the corresponding configuration: Multi-family occupancy dwelling for residential configuration, Retail for commercial configuration, Office for office configuration, and Gymnasium for convention configuration (Table 3.1). The Construction Set was set to Building Type (default) with the following materials chosen:

- Exterior walls – Wall 4 in. concrete with 2 in. insulation on the inside (U=0.6941)
- Interior walls – Hollow concrete blocks (U=1.2718)
- Ground floor slabs – Standard floor construction (2002 UK Regulations) (U=0.2499)
- Roofs – Flat roof (2002 UK Regulations) (U=0.2497)
- Upper floors – 2 in. Light weigh concrete floor deck (U=2.9968)

- Doors – Wooden door (U=2.1944)
- Exterior windows – Single-glazed windows – domestic (U=4.8293)
- Interior windows – Single-glazed windows – domestic (U=3.2983)
- Skylights – Polycarbonate Double-glazed Roof lights (U=3.7299)

The weather is set to the Manila, Philippines weather, as it is the closest location to Davao City with available data. The HVAC system was set to none and the heating and cooling operations were set to off continuously. Under the MacroFlo application, all openings on the exterior were set to sliding door opening type with 50% openable area. The simulation period was set from June 1 to June 30, with June 17 as the experimental design day selected.

To determine the air movement in the stacks, the volume flow in and out of the stack openings under the VistaPro application were analyzed. For the interior temperature, the operative temperature values of the rooms and the interior hallways of the simulation models were recorded. The interior wind velocity data were obtained using the MicroFlo application, and analyzed using the filled velocity contour graph.

To determine the air movement in the stacks, the volume flow in and out of the stack openings under the VistaPro application were analyzed. The changing volume of air flowing in and out of openings at different floor levels were used to determine if the air is flowing upward or downward along the stack.

Comparative analysis between the results of the ATM-inspired simulation models and the conventional models was done for the interior wind velocity and the operative temperature to compare the efficiency of the ATM-inspired models. Moreover, the interior wind velocity and the operative temperature were evaluated if they reached the minimal air velocity required and the comfortable temperature range of 20-25°C, respectively. Minimal air velocity was obtained from Figure 6 from the study of Candido and de Dear (2011) that proposes a guideline for thermal and air movement acceptability in naturally ventilated buildings in Brazil.

Figure 6. Minimal Air Velocity

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the significant parts of African termite mounds gathered and identified from extensive review of termite mound morphology and ventilation studies, with the terms they are labelled to in published literatures enumerated in the first column. The second column of the table discusses the important and general function of the part in relation to ventilation and gas exchange in the mound. The third and final column are the architectural counterparts integrated in the ATM-inspired natural

ventilation system design and their corresponding function to architecture, after analyzing the function of each mound part and what architectural elements can best emulate them.

Table 1. Emulation of the Parts of African Termite Mounds to Its Architectural Counterpart

<i>Parts and mechanism of the mound</i>	<i>Function to the mound</i>	<i>Architectural simulation counterpart</i>	<i>Function to architecture</i>
Egress tunnel	Pores of the enclosed mound that allow respiratory gas exchange	External surface windows	Allows entry of air into interior spaces
Surface conduits	Underlie the entire surface of the mound and serves as entry of high-frequency turbulent winds		
Tunnel reticulum	Tunnels where mixed forced and natural convection occur and where medium frequency wind are filtered	Underfloor air spaces	Drive air flow to reach farther through turbulent winds and opening on the floor on innermost room areas
Subterranean tunnels	Passageway of air driven by natural convection; connects the bottom part of the nest to the vertical tunnels in the upper part and surface of the mound	"Stacks" (vertical air spaces located at different positions in each building)	Passageway of air in the building to drive air movement through pressure differences and induced flow
Nest	The core of the termite habitat that shelters the young termites and fungi and is composed of galleries separated by thin perforated walls	Interior space / rooms	Main space of the building, sometimes separated by interior partitions, occupied by the building users
Chimney	Drives gas exchange in and out from the nest to the networks of tunnels through natural convection	Main stack / "chimney"	Drives air to and from the inner core of the building through natural convection and induced flow

The first part of the simulation was to simulate the air movement in the stacks to determine if it will function similarly to the solar-powered ventilation of African termite mounds. Simulation results show that air movement in the stacks of the ATM-inspired natural ventilation system design did not coincide with the path of solar heat unlike in termite mounds. Results for the 4 simulation tests, for 8:30 AM, 12:30 PM, 4:30 PM and 8:30 PM showed different results as compared to the air movement in African termite mounds.

Based on the simulation results, air movement in the east stack of the nine building footprints at 8:30 AM show a downward air movement except for the square atrium shape with interior partitions, contrary to the expected upward air movement since the sun directly heats the east direction in the morning. In the midday, stacks in the north, northwest and northeast directions show conforming results. However, stacks in the other directions do not, and it can be seen that the general air movement in all sides in all shapes is upward. This trend follows in the afternoon and night simulation results as well. Air movement in all sides is upward and do not conform to the expected results.

The unexpected results for air movement may be accounted to the difference in the overall structure of termite mounds and buildings, as well as the material used in both structures. For the building design, the stacks are not connected with each other. This may have reduced the cohesive air movement in the mound, resulting to similar air movement directions in all sides, although it has not been determined on which stacks in the building is the velocity of air movement the least or greatest. Determining this will help in determining more accurately the effect of solar radiation to the air movement in the stacks.

The results of the CFD simulation for interior wind velocity show that there are slower wind velocities in the ATM-inspired simulation models compared to the conventional model, from 0 to 0.55 m/s and greater than 1.2 m/s in some areas. This may be due to the presence of the stacks in the mimicked

design that creates interior partitions in the building, obstructing the continuous flow of air from the windows. Compared to the conventional models with no stacks, the movement of air is continuous from the windows and can spread to the interiors of the building directly. The recorded air velocity is within the range of 90% acceptability based on the study of Candido and de Dear (2011) shown in Figure 6, based also on the operative temperatures recorded.

For all building simulation models, it was observed that the interior wind velocity is greater in the upper storeys compared to the lower storeys. This can be due to the fact that weather conditions are more intense as the elevation gets higher. Moreover, interior wind velocity is also noticeably greater in the center, specifically in the main stack of the ATM-inspired models. The wind velocity is greatest in the main stack and around the window and stack openings, while the periphery or the rooms have lesser velocities.

Comparing the temperature of the conventional model and the ATM-inspired design, it can be observed that the interior room temperatures in the two models have close values. Both the conventional and the design have values close to 25°C minimum temperature and 32° maximum temperatures in all configurations of all building footprint shapes, particularly in the rooms, which have access to exterior windows. However, there is a noticeable difference between the temperature of the interior hallways of the ATM-inspired model with interior partitions and the interior hallways of the conventional model with interior partitions. The operative temperature in the hallways of the mimicked design is significantly lower.

Figure 7. Operative Temperature for Simulation Model with Configurations: Cross-Shape, 25 Storey, with Interior Partition, 2h Depth, 44% Wall Opening

Figure 8. Operative Temperature for Simulation Model with Configurations: L-shape, 10 Storey – with Interior Partition – 2h Depth – 44% Wall Opening

Figure 9. Operative Temperature for Simulation Model with Configurations: T-shape, 10 Storey – with Interior Partition – 4h Depth – 78% Wall Opening

Figure 10. Operative Temperature for Simulation Model with Configurations: U-Shape, 10 Storey – with No Interior Partition - 5h Depth – 44% Wall Opening

Figure 11. Operative Temperature for Simulation Model with Configurations: H-Shape, 25 Storey, with Interior Partition, 4h Depth, 78% Wall Opening

Figure 12. Operative Temperature for Simulation Model with Configurations: Square Atrium, 25 Storey, with Interior Partition, 2h Depth, 78% Wall Opening

Figure 13. Operative Temperature for Simulation Model with Configurations: Rectangular, 10 Storey – with Interior Partition – 4h Depth – 78% Wall Opening

Figure 14. Operative Temperature for Simulation Model with Configurations: Triangular, 10 Storey, with Interior Partition, 2h Depth, 78% Wall Opening

Figure 15. Operative Temperature for Simulation Model with Configurations: Trapezoidal, 25 Storey, with Interior Partition, 4h Depth, 78% Wall Opening

The close values of temperature in the rooms of the two types of model may be due to the range of the external ambient temperature, where the minimum dry bulb temperature is 26.44°C and the maximum dry bulb temperature is 35.04°C. The interior temperature is lower than the external average temperature in both ATM-inspired and conventional model. Previous studies, as that of [2] which also studied the efficiency of natural ventilation system, showed that the overheating period has not been fully eliminated although the temperature has been decreased, due to the absence of other passive or active cooling strategies, and this may also be applied in this study. A greater decrease in the interior temperature may be achieved if the ATM-inspired design will be coupled with other active or passive cooling strategies. Close temperature in the rooms between the ATM-inspired design models and the conventional model maybe attributed to similar settings, such as the presence of windows.

The effect of the stack in the mimicked design models can be more evident in the interior hallways. In the conventional model, the hallways have no openings, contributing to a raised interior temperature exceeding 30°C, specifically in the cross shape, L-shape, T-shape, atrium shape and trapezoid shape. However, the temperature in their corresponding ATM-inspired design models is significantly lower. This is due to the presence of the stack openings that provide opening to the interior hallways, which have contributed to achieving optimal interior room temperature. Based on the simulation data, the optimal interior temperature is between 25°C to 32°C. For the building depth, greater wind velocity is obtained with a smaller room depth, particularly a depth of $2h$. This is the optimum building depth that results to the greatest wind velocity, although the room temperature is same for all building depths. For the building with no interior partitions, the most optimal depth is still the less deep depth which is $5h$. A greater building depth will lessen the chances of air to reach the innermost parts of the building.

For the building height, as observed, there is greater wind velocities as the elevation gets higher, and there is greater wind velocity in the upper floors. For the wall opening, the minimum and maximum temperature in both 44% and 78% wall opening are close to each other. However, the wind velocity in the models with 78% wall opening are greater.

Based on the simulation results, there is lower temperature when the building footprint is facing or oriented towards the north and south directions if the building has no interior partitions, and when the building footprint is facing or oriented towards the south and southwest directions if the building has interior partitions.

CONCLUSION

Termites build impressive termite mounds that is consist of tunnels and airspaces that provide ventilation to the subterranean nest where the termites and their larvae are. Recent studies [4,5,7]

show that African termite mounds (ATM) are driven by solar-powered ventilation where air flow follows temperature variations as different parts of the mound get heated directly by the sun at different times of the day.

This ventilation mechanism and the parts of African termite mounds have been mimicked to achieve a natural ventilation system design for buildings, through architectural elements such as vertical air stacks, underfloor airspaces, main chimney, and building openings. Various configurations of the building footprint shape, depth, percentage of wall openings, building height and orientation and type of occupancy have been simulated through a computer simulation software to identify which configuration integrated with the ATM-inspired natural ventilation system design is most efficient through simulating air movement, interior wind velocity and operative temperature.

The simulation results show that air movement in the ATM-inspired models did not follow diurnal temperature oscillations similar to that of solar-heat African termite mounds. The interior wind velocity was found to be slower in the ATM-inspired models compared to the conventional models. Moreover, operative temperature resulted to be lower in the interior hallways of ATM-inspired models compared in the conventional models, and values of operative temperature for all different configurations of ATM-inspired models were within close values with each other, ranging from 24°C to 32°C.

Air movement for the stacks in some directions did not conform to the expected results meanwhile some stacks did. The difference in the results have not been dwelt upon in the study, but it may be attributed to the different structure and material of the mound and the building, or to the biomimicry translation of the parts of the termite mound. A more detailed study can be done to check whether the air movement in vertical air stacks will be influenced by temperature gradients caused by direct solar heat.

Interior wind velocity is found to be slower in ATM-inspired models compared in conventional models. There is greater wind velocity in the upper stories, near window openings and inside the vertical air stacks. Hence, there is air flow in the stacks that drive ventilation inside the building. Moreover, operative temperature is found to be lower in the interior hallways with no external openings of ATM-inspired models. For all configurations, the operative temperature fell between the range of 24°C to 32°C. The miniscule differences in the operative temperatures of the ATM-inspired models and conventional models may be attributed to the lack of additional active and passive cooling strategies implied. Based on the different configurations simulated, most efficient results were seen from models with smaller building depth, higher building height and greater wall openings.

In summary, the integration of ATM-inspired natural ventilation system contributed to the comfortable temperature and ventilation inside the simulate building models. It can decrease the operative temperature, especially in interior spaces with no access to external openings. It is recommended to use other ways to test and analyze the efficiency of biomimicry aside from computer simulation (i.e. physical simulation, etc.). To further improve the performance of ventilation inside the building, additional active and passive cooling strategies may be incorporated. Further studies may adapt this study by improving the mimicry and translation of mound elements and processes to architectural elements, or by focusing on a single or only a few building configurations to compare at once, to be able to give more specific analysis and comparison.

REFERENCES

1. C. Cândido, R. Lamberts, R. D. Dear, L. Bittencourt, and R. D. Vecchi, "Towards a Brazilian standard for naturally ventilated buildings: Guidelines for thermal and air movement acceptability," *Building Research & Information*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 145–153, 2011, doi: 10.1080/09613218.2011.557858.
2. S. Khelil and N. Zemmouri, "Biomimetic: A new strategy for a passive sustainable ventilation system design in hot and arid regions," *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 2821–2830, 2018, doi: 10.1007/s13762-018-2168-y.

3. H. King, S. Ocko, and L. Mahadevan, "Termite mounds harness diurnal temperature oscillations for ventilation," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 112, no. 37, pp. 11589–11593, 2015, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1423242112.
4. J. Korb, "Thermoregulation and ventilation of termite mounds," *Naturwissenschaften*, vol. 90, no. 5, pp. 212–219, 2003, doi: 10.1007/s00114-002-0401-4.
5. J. Korb and K. E. Linsenmair, "Thermoregulation of termite mounds: What role does ambient temperature and metabolism of the colony play?," *Insectes Sociaux*, vol. 47, pp. 357–363, 2000, doi: 10.1007/PL00001729.
6. M. Lüscher, "Air conditioned termite nests," *Scientific American*, vol. 238, no. 1, pp. 138–145, 1961.
7. S. A. Ocko, H. King, D. Andreen, P. Bardunias, J. S. Turner, R. Soar, and L. Mahadevan, "Solar-powered ventilation of African termite mounds," *Journal of Experimental Biology*, vol. 220, no. 17, pp. 3260–3269, 2017, doi: 10.1242/jeb.160895.
8. J. S. Turner, "On the mound of *Macrotermes michaelseni* as an organ of respiratory gas exchange," *Physiological and Biochemical Zoology*, vol. 74, no. 6, pp. 798–822, 2001, doi: 10.1086/323990.
9. J. S. Turner and R. C. Soar, "Beyond biomimicry: What termites can tell us about realizing the living building," in *1st International Conference on Industrialised, Integrated, Intelligent Construction (I3CON)*, 2008, pp. 221–226.
10. M. Worall, "Homeostasis in nature: Nest building termites and intelligent buildings," *Intelligent Buildings International*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 87–95, 2011, doi: 10.1080/17508975.2011.582333.

